

Urea supergranules (USG) produced significantly higher yields (3.9 t/ha) than the other N sources (see table). Yields with split-applied urea and sulfur-coated

urea were similar, and significantly higher than with urea at transplanting. Yields varied from 2.3 to 4.4 t/ha. USG

performed best at 40 kg N/ha, but at higher N levels was as effective as split-applied urea and sulfur-coated urea. \mathcal{L}

Residual effect of three N sources and application rates on irrigated lowland rices

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Much of the available information on residual effects of N fertilizers is from studies conducted on upland or nonsubmerged soils. N fertilizer behavior in lowland or submerged conditions is distinctly different.

We studied the residual effects of N on irrigated wetland rice in an experiment after the International Network on Soil Fertility and Fertilizer Evaluation for Rice (INSFFER) trial. Soil was a plinthic Vertic Tropaquept, fine clayey, nonacid, and isohyperthermic at Maros, South Sulawesi, Indonesia. IR30 was planted. Treatments of the previous experiment are in the table.

During vegetative growth, there were no distinct visual differences among the treatments. Grain yield, panicles/m², percent filled grains, 100-grain weight,

Grain yield, yield components, and soil pH as affected by residual N from 3 sources at 3 rates on irrigated lowland rice, Maros, Indonesia.

N rate (kg/ha)	Previous treatment ^a		Grain yield (t/ha)	Productive tillers/m ²	Filled grain (%)	100 grain wt (g)	Height (cm)	soil pH at harvest
	Source	Method						
29	Control		3.7	248	90	2.0	72	5.8
	U	2/3 AP, 1/3 PI	3.5	216	91	2.0	67	5.9
	SCU	BI, AP	3.8	237	90	2.0	70	5.9
	USG	Hand placed 10-12 cm deep	3.8	255	90	2.0	71	5.9
58	U	2/3 AP, 1/3PI	4.3	263	91	2.0	72	5.9
	SCU	BI, AP	3.6	254	92	2.0	71	5.9
	USG	Hand placed 10-12 cm deep	3.3	235	90	1.9	68	6.0
87	U	2/3 AP, 1/3 PI	3.9	262	91	1.9	70	5.8
	SCU	BI, AP	4.2	263	92	2.0	75	5.9
	USG	Hand placed 10-12 cm deep	3.6	226	91	2.0	69	5.9
116	U	2/3 AP, 1/3 PI	3.6	228	90	1.9	71	6.0
	SCU	BI, AP	4.3	249	91	2.0	75	5.9
	USG	Hand placed 10-12 cm deep	3.8	258	91	2.0	74	5.9
Test of significance			ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
CV (%)			16.2	12.6	10.8	8.6	12.0	10.0

^a U = urea, SCU = sulfur-coated urea, USG = urea supergranule, AP = at planting, PI = panicle initiation, and BI = broadcast and incorporated.

plant height at harvest, and soil pH at harvest indicated no significant differences among the treatments (see table). Even at the highest application

rate (116 kg N/ha), urea, sulfur-coated urea, and urea supergranules had no carry-over effect on the following rice crop. \mathcal{L}

A simple solution to sulfur deficiency, and an extension technique

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In Apr 1983, a farmer leader from a barrio near MORIF came to the Institute with a problem. He had applied 2 bags of urea/ha 10 d earlier but plants had remained yellow and stunted.

We visited the field and identified S deficiency as the problem. Instead of telling the farmer to apply ammonium sulfate, we established a simple

Mean results of a simple experiment to solve sulfur deficiency in a farmer's field, South Sulawesi, Indonesia.

Parameter	Control	Urea	Ammonium sulfate	Urea + S	LSD (%)
Dry wt (g/5 hills) 30 d after fertilizer application	78	83	265	257	46
Plant ht (cm) at harvest	58	62	76	74	10
Panicles (no./m ²)	214	270	388	350	78
Spikelets (no./panicle)	92	102	116	108	ns
Filled grains (%)	84	85	86	86	ns
Grain weight (g/1000)	21	21	22	21	ns
Grain yield (t/ha), 14% moisture	2.5	3.0	5.0	4.8	0.85
Straw yield (t/ha), sun-dried	3.1	3.4	4.9	4.9	0.78
Maturity (days from planting to harvesting)	98	98	90	90	